

Phenotypic rate and state are decoupled in response to river-to-lake transitions in cichlid fishes

Supplementary Tables and Figures

Table S1. Table S1. Morphological data used in the study. Values are species means. Linear distances are ln-transformed. Abbreviations: standard length (SL), ascending process of the premaxilla (AP), mandible (mandible), maxilla (maxilla), premaxilla (premax), mechanical advantage closing (MA close), head length (HL), head depth (HD), snout length (SnL), body depth (BD), caudal peduncle depth (CPD), caudal peduncle length (CLP), kinematic transmission (kt), kinesis (kinesis), and kinematic asynchrony (ka), ecosystem type (River or Lake), and lake identity (the specific lake of origin).

*See corresponding dryad file (“Supporting_Data_dryad.csv”).

Table S2. Clades used to assess time-scaling of evolutionary rates. Taxa are the two species used to define the clades, their clade age, and the clade rates estimated from BM-simulated and the observed traits.

Taxa1	Taxa2	Clade age	Clade rate simulated	Clade rate observed
<i>Etoplus_suratensis</i>	<i>Paretroplus_polyactis</i>	68.18	0.0562	0.0263
<i>Katria_katria</i>	<i>Paratilapia_polleni</i>	48.277	0.0551	0.0275
<i>Astronotus_ocellatus</i>	<i>Gymnogeophagus_gymnogenys</i>	50.514	0.0566	0.0369
<i>Andinoacara_latifrons</i>	<i>Cleithracara_maronii</i>	38.288	0.0557	0.0402
<i>Symphysodon_aequifasciatus</i>	<i>Mesonauta_insignis</i>	18.83	0.0609	0.0434
<i>Cribroheros_alfari</i>	<i>Herotilapia_multispinosa</i>	19.843	0.0512	0.0422
<i>Nandopsis_tetracanthus</i>	<i>Nandopsis_haitiensis</i>	13.576	0.0524	0.0417
<i>Herichthys_cyanoguttatus</i>	<i>Vieja_maculicauda</i>	9.883	0.0552	0.0723
<i>Trichromis_salvini</i>	<i>Thorichthys_helleri</i>	12.263	0.0512	0.0706
<i>Kronoheros_umbrifer</i>	<i>Caquetaia_kraussii</i>	13.096	0.0718	0.064
<i>Amatitlania_nigrofasciata</i>	<i>Petenia_splendida</i>	10.0556	0.0691	0.0677
<i>Mayaheros_urophthalmus</i>	<i>Amphilophus_amarillo</i>	10.068	0.0622	0.0674
<i>Tylochromis_poylepis</i>	<i>Tylochromis_intermedius</i>	34	0.0546	0.0273
<i>Pelvicachromis_rolofi</i>	<i>Parananochromis_longirostris</i>	31.115	0.0552	0.0277
<i>Pelamtochromis_buettikoferi</i>	<i>Anomalochromis_thomasi</i>	46.012	0.0559	0.0548
<i>Oreochromis_leucostictus</i>	<i>Oreochromis_karongae</i>	17.793	0.0587	0.0603
<i>Oreochromis_niloticus</i>	<i>Oreochromis_aureus</i>	9.959	0.0519	0.0579
<i>Sarotherodon_galilaeus</i>	<i>Sarotherodon_lamprechti</i>	1.512	0.0827	0.1892
<i>Pungu_maclareni</i>	<i>Sarotherodon_caroli</i>	1.058	0.0455	0.1842
<i>Coptodon_deckerti</i>	<i>Coptodon_zillii</i>	27.626	0.0578	0.0668
<i>Bathybates_fasciatus</i>	<i>Tilapia_sparrmani</i>	23.305	0.0546	0.0566
<i>Lepidolamprologus_elongatus</i>	<i>Telmatochromis_dhonti</i>	11.718	0.0563	0.0745
<i>Cyphotilapia_frontosa</i>	<i>Aulocranus_dewindti</i>	15.417	0.0622	0.0683

Sargochromis_codringtoni	Pseudocrilabrus_philander	11.145	0.0578	0.0697
Tropheus_moorii	Ctenochromis_horei	5.943	0.0586	0.1034
Astatotilapia_burtoni	Haplochromis_desfontainii	6.941	0.0529	0.0666
Diplotaxodon_greenwoodi	Rhamphochromis_esox	1.12	0.0788	0.1615
Astatotilapia_calliptera	Labeotropheus_fuelleborni	2.135	0.0633	0.179
Placidochromis_milomo	Ctenopharynx_intermedius	1.2	0.102	0.285

Table S3. Evolutionary model fitting for head shape, jaw functional morphology, and mechanical properties of the jaws across cichlid fishes. Theta estimates are shown for the best model: single-optimum (OU1) or multi-optima (OUM) models (river and lake).

Class of traits/Best model	Trait	OU1	River optimum	Lake optimum
Shape (OUM)	Head length	--	0.012	0.012
	Head depth	--	-0.026	-0.129
	Snout length	--	-0.008	0.013
Functional (OUM)	Ascending process	--	0.068	-0.188
	Premaxilla	--	0.056	0.026
	Maxilla	--	0.164	0.001
	Mandible	--	0.103	0.032
Mechanical (OU1)	Kinematic transition	0.818	--	--
	Kinesis	0.259	--	--
	Kinematic asynchrony	0.136	--	--

$$\textit{Coincident} = b_c / b_{bg}$$

$$\textit{Delayed} = b_d / b_{bg}$$

Figure S1. Diagram indicating how rate ratios were calculated for coincident and delayed rate shifts associated with a hypothetical river-to-lake transition. River (gray) and lake (red) taxa are denoted with circles. The lake radiation is highlighted in the gray box.

Figure S2. Posterior estimates of key parameters across models with different priors on the number of rate shifts using the random local clock model, as in Figure 4 of the main text, as well as an Uncorrelated lognormal model.

Figure S3. Many-to-one-mapping of functional morphology (PC bi-plot) to mechanical properties of the jaws. See Figure 2 in the main text for loadings along each axis.